

Dealing with multilingualism in the DACH and DHd association

For the AG Multilingual DH in the DHd (alphabetical): Till Grallert, Xenia Monika Kudela, Jonas Müller-Laackman, Eliese-Sophia Lincke, Colinda Lindermann, Jana Mende, Larissa Schmid

Introduction

A German-speaking space imagined as a monolingual geographical region is a romantic political fiction. Its borders and boundaries are left unclear by its advocates for good reasons or are equated with the current national territories of Germany, Austria, and some cantons of Switzerland. However, this geographical and political space is historically the center of life of multilingual societies and communities and the destination of most diverse migration movements, which have further diversified the multilingualism of German native speakers. Science policy clearly frames this space as an immigration space in which the German language does not play a central role as a criterion for access, participation or even quality in scientific discourse. For example, in the academic year 2022, more than a quarter of all new students were foreign nationals.¹ It is therefore not surprising when the Digital Humanities association in the German-speaking world formulates the following characteristics, among others, as typical of the research field in its Digital Humanities 2020 theses: "Transcending disciplinary, linguistic, cultural, and national borders and adopting holistic perspectives".² These transgressions should then also show up in DH-characteristic cooperations and teams.

Multilingualism is a precondition and expression of such border crossings on several levels: The multilingual competence of individual researchers and multilingual research teams make international projects possible. Research projects with multilingual content and methods enable holistic perspectives and thus address the expectations of digital humanities projects to a particular degree.

¹ https://www.destatis.de/DE/Presse/Pressemitteilungen/2023/03/PD23_097_213.html, 20.05.2023.

² <https://dig-hum.de/thesen-digital-humanities-2020>, 20.05.2023.

At the same time, there is a focus on German as the working language and the language of the research subject within the DHd, as can be seen in its statutes.³ First of all, the German-speaking area is mentioned in the name as an overarching cohesion and named "Germany and the German-speaking countries and regions". This area, however, historically and currently encompasses a great variety of languages. However, the German language is then cited as a monolingual feature when the association explicitly addresses "German-speaking humanities scholars and cultural scientists as well as computer scientists". From a multilingual perspective, the question is how do these concepts fit together? What understanding of multilingualism is expressed here?

In everyday understanding, multilingualism is often equated with the individual knowledge of a person, which beyond that has no political or social relevance. In multilingualism research, which originated in linguistics, multilingualism is understood on the one hand as individual-psychological phenomena of language acquisition of more than one language, and on the other hand as social and societal uses of more than one language in groups, societies, countries, and institutions.

In the digital humanities, a different concept of multilingualism has established itself both at the meta-level and at the object-level. On the one hand, it addresses the political and social functions of multilingualism or monolingualism as well as attitudes towards it⁴ and problematizes monolingual approaches to objects, methods, and tools. On the other hand, it often deals with concrete problems caused by monolingualism when working with digital methods, especially when using non-Latin scripts, which occur particularly frequently in digital projects. These two problem areas are closely related.

Considering the current desire of the DHd to cross linguistic and national borders, this would address an urgent concern of multilingual DH work. However, it is clear from the statutes that there seem to be contradictions, even in the self-description, as to what role multilingualism and what role German should have within the association. At this point, this paper will make some suggestions for a multilingual concept of the DHd that takes into account both multilingualism and the role of the German language.

³ <https://dig-hum.de/dhd-satzung>, 20.05.2023.

⁴ Vgl. Spence, P. J. & Brandao, R., (2021) "Towards Language Sensitivity and Diversity in the Digital Humanities", *Digital Studies / Le champ numérique* 11(1).

1. We suggest that the so-called "Kleine Fächer" be given more support.

According to its own statement, the association "Digital Humanities in the German-speaking world" serves the "self-organization of a new transdisciplinary community and represents its interests".⁵ In 2023, this transdisciplinary community always includes the so-called "Kleine Fächer"⁶ (small subjects), with an above-average number of multilingual subjects. Although they shape academic discourse across disciplinary boundaries, they are often underrepresented. The DHd association can do groundbreaking work here by promoting the presence of the "Kleine Fächer" and offering marginalized disciplines space within the framework of its vision of a transdisciplinary representation of interests.

This goes hand in hand with a revision of routine processes. That applies, for example, to the review process for the DHd conferences, which often represents a disproportionately high barrier, especially for submissions from smaller disciplines. Reviewers are not necessarily always familiar with the sometimes highly specialized subject discourses. For this reason, reviewers from marginalized and less established disciplines should also be involved, as they can make a better assessment of subject-specific submissions. In this way, conferences and publications can be made more widely accessible and the DHd association can better address its vision of a transdisciplinary representation of interests.

With such an expansion, DHd can also attract new members, who currently would not join because they do not find themselves in the strongly German-oriented orientation (examples are known to the authors).

⁵ <https://dig-hum.de/thesen-digital-humanities-2020>, 20.05.2023.

⁶ <https://www.kleinefaecher.de/>, 20.05.2023.

2. We invite the association to continue to deal with multilingualism and to develop an appropriate concept for addressing issues with multilingualism (suggestions and questions can be found below)

At the DHd 2023, the question of whether to allow presentations in languages other than German came up again, which highlights a central problem: the DHd association needs to clarify the question of whether it sees itself as representing the interests of "digital humanities in the German-speaking world" or those of "German-speaking humanities and cultural studies scholars and computer scientists".

In his contribution *Zur Sprachenfrage bei der DHd-Jahrestagung*⁷ (On the Language Question at the DHd Annual Conference), Christof Schöch discussed the topic for the DHd Board as early as 2020. The focus on German as the primary language of presentation is justified by the fact that this would lower the entry hurdles for young scientists. This would be in line with the idea of the DHd association as an association "in German". Although it is emphasized that "the language of the submission is not a criterion for the review process", the current practice creates an exclusive scientific space that puts people in the German-speaking world who have not learned German as their first language at a disadvantage.

The association promotes German as a first language in German-speaking countries. This should not be at the expense of other languages that are equally represented in this space. Therefore, we suggest dealing pragmatically and constructively with non-German-language contributions and removing the justification clause for other languages from future CfPs. Instead, one could encourage and invite contributions to be submitted or presented in German even in the case of uncertainties in regard to language skills. The CfP should also be published in English.

If the DHd association sees itself as representing the interests of the "Digital Humanities in the German-speaking world", multilingualism must also be addressed in concrete working practice beyond the conferences. In an increasingly international scientific

⁷ <https://dhd-blog.org/?p=13908>, 20.05.2023.

community, a first approach would be to not limit the association's presence to a German-language website. Analogous to the internationalization of the ADHO website, at least an English version of the website should be available as a source of information. This can then contain a corresponding reference to the promotion of German as a language of science and DH.

In general, the association should focus the topic of multilingualism less exclusively on German, which is in any case strongly represented among the members of the association and its scholarly community. The DHd should understand multilingualism as a potential source of enrichment for discourses in and outside the concrete work of the association.

3. We suggest rethinking the DHd association as an umbrella organization representing the interests of all DH communities in the German-speaking area (broader/wider/more open)

The DHd association sees itself as the representative of the Digital Humanities in the German-speaking world. However, the association currently represents only a part of the communities that practice digital humanities. Particularly in multilingual disciplines, separate interest groups often emerge that do not see themselves as effectively represented in the DHd. (e.g. Historical Middle East Data Alliance⁸, Digital Arabic Studies/DOT⁹, Digital Ancient Studies, ...).

We see the development of different communities along the often historically grown disciplinary borders as a loss of great potential that the association could bring forth by bundling these communities. With the active opening of the association and the creation of interesting offerings for disciplines that have not been represented so far, or only to a limited extent, the association can not only better address its vision, but it also appears more effectively as a representation of interests to the outside world.

⁸ <https://github.com/Hist-ME>, 20.05.2023.

⁹ <https://dot2022.de/workshop-digital-humanities>, 20.05.2023.

This also applies, among other things, to the promotion of young researchers, who already struggle at the institutional level with the limited capacities of small disciplines. Better integration of students and doctoral candidates from marginalized disciplines promotes the visibility of those disciplines and the diversity of the digital humanities in the German-speaking world, and it can ensure better synergizing in practice and the promotion of a new internationally oriented scientific culture.

4. We suggest that disciplinary communities get more involved in the work of the association in order to strengthen the representation of multilingual disciplines in the German-speaking world.

We call on working groups and interest groups outside the DHd association to actively participate in the association, to present projects with a multilingual orientation on the DHd website and to promote interdisciplinary exchange. Within the framework of the association, work in the working groups, participation in the DHd conferences, and the creative, critical, and constructive introduction of new topics and perspectives is particularly useful for this purpose.

Proposals for Action

In light of the points described here, we recommend the implementation of the following four proposals for action to improve the handling of multilingualism in the DHd association:

- The justification clause in the Call for Papers should be removed; instead it should constructively invite to face linguistic limitations.
- The Call for Papers should be published in English as well.
- Linguistically competent or multilingual peer reviewers (from the corresponding "Kleine Fächer") should be involved.
- The DHd website should be translated at least into English (other languages in German-speaking countries would be desirable in the long term).

The members of the Multilingual DH WG are happy to contribute to the development and implementation of these and other points to promote multilingualism in the association and in the digital humanities.